

**Bridging Language Gaps in Real-time:
Investigating University Students' Self-Initiated Use of Speech-to-Text Translation in English Language Classrooms**

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Exploratory Factor Analysis

```
jmv::efa(
  data = data,
  vars = vars(Understand teacher clearly, Follow along the lecture, Comprehend sentences and expression, Understand
unfamiliar vocabulary, Save time understanding the lesson, Identify grammar patterns, Feeling less lost in the discussion, Focus
better in the lesson, Easy to recall lesson content, Complete assigned task accurately, Engaged in class, Confident to participate,
Encouraged to ask question, Focused on class discussion, Reduced anxiety in learning, Less hesitation to participate, Encouraged
to contribute and collaborate, Increased interest in learning),
  nFactorMethod = "eigen",
  minEigen = 1,
  extraction = "pa",
  eigen = TRUE,
  factorCor = TRUE,
  factorSummary = TRUE,
  modelFit = TRUE,
  kmo = TRUE,
  bartlett = TRUE,
  factorScoreMethod = "Bartlett")
```

Factor Loadings

	Factor		Uniqueness
	1	2	
Understand teacher clearly	0.562		0.496
Follow along the lecture	0.719		0.427
Comprehend sentences and expression	0.754		0.427
Understand unfamiliar vocabulary	0.666		0.557
Save time understanding the lesson	0.846		0.362
Identify grammar patterns	0.686		0.512
Feeling less lost in the discussion	0.632		0.441
Focus better in the lesson	0.732		0.514
Easy to recall lesson content	0.803		0.369
Complete assigned task accurately	0.717		0.433
Engaged in class		0.511	0.443
Confident to participate		0.733	0.346
Encouraged to ask question		0.822	0.412
Focused on class discussion		0.866	0.283
Reduced anxiety in learning		0.903	0.298

Factor Loadings

	Factor		Uniqueness
	1	2	
Less hesitation to participate		0.599	0.430
Encouraged to contribute and collaborate		0.686	0.284
Increased interest in learning		0.829	0.291

Note. 'Principal axis factoring' extraction method was used in combination with a 'oblimin' rotation

Factor Statistics

Summary

Factor	SS Loadings	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.68	31.6	31.6
2	5.00	27.8	59.3

Inter-Factor Correlations

	1	2
1	—	0.731
2		—

Model Fit Measures

RMSEA	RMSEA 90% CI		TLI	BIC	Model Test		
	Lower	Upper			χ^2	df	p
0.0634	0.0509	0.0763	0.947	-414	225	118	<.001

Assumption Checks

Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

χ^2	df	p
2793	153	<.001

KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy

	MSA
Overall	0.952
Understand teacher clearly	0.946
Follow along the lecture	0.962

KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy

	MSA
Comprehend sentences and expression	0.936
Understand unfamiliar vocabulary	0.950
Save time understanding the lesson	0.954
Identify grammar patterns	0.946
Feeling less lost in the discussion	0.966
Focus better in the lesson	0.973
Easy to recall lesson content	0.962
Complete assigned task accurately	0.946
Engaged in class	0.951
Confident to participate	0.962
Encouraged to ask question	0.964
Focused on class discussion	0.947
Reduced anxiety in learning	0.953
Less hesitation to participate	0.951
Encouraged to contribute and collaborate	0.938
Increased interest in learning	0.943

Eigenvalues

Initial Eigenvalues

Factor	Eigenvalue
1	9.41367
2	1.09810
3	0.25875
4	0.16765
5	0.10180
6	0.09145
7	0.00780
8	-0.03031
9	-0.07786
10	-0.08053
11	-0.12057
12	-0.13139
13	-0.15353
14	-0.18296
15	-0.19560

Initial Eigenvalues

Factor	Eigenvalue
16	-0.23381
17	-0.25257
18	-0.26617

Reliability Analysis

```
jmv::reliability(  
  data = data,  
  vars = vars(Understand teacher clearly, Follow along the lecture, Comprehend sentences and expression,  
  Understand unfamiliar vocabulary, Save time understanding the lesson, Identify grammar patterns, Feeling less lost  
  in the discussion, Focus better in the lesson, Easy to recall lesson content, Complete assigned task accurately,  
  Engaged in class, Confident to participate, Encouraged to ask question, Focused on class discussion, Reduced  
  anxiety in learning, Less hesitation to participate, Encouraged to contribute and collaborate, Increased interest in  
  learning),  
  meanScale = TRUE,  
  sdScale = TRUE,  
  alphaItems = TRUE,  
  meanItems = TRUE,  
  sdItems = TRUE,  
  itemRestCor = TRUE)
```

Scale Reliability Statistics

	Mean	SD	Cronbach's α
scale	4.19	0.572	0.951

Item Reliability Statistics

	Mean	SD	Item-rest correlation	If item dropped Cronbach's α
Understand teacher clearly	4.27	0.733	0.686	0.949
Follow along the lecture	4.25	0.744	0.706	0.948
Comprehend sentences and expression	4.21	0.786	0.696	0.948
Understand unfamiliar vocabulary	4.34	0.747	0.610	0.950
Save time understanding the lesson	4.15	0.793	0.715	0.948
Identify grammar patterns	3.92	0.849	0.645	0.950
Feeling less lost in the discussion	4.23	0.744	0.714	0.948

Item Reliability Statistics

	Mean	SD	Item-rest correlation	If item dropped Cronbach's α
Focus better in the lesson	4.13	0.788	0.627	0.950
Easy to recall lesson content	4.18	0.754	0.726	0.948
Complete assigned task accurately	4.20	0.767	0.703	0.948
Engaged in class	4.17	0.802	0.720	0.948
Confident to participate	4.16	0.810	0.742	0.948
Encouraged to ask question	4.15	0.789	0.653	0.949
Focused on class discussion	4.18	0.779	0.738	0.948
Reduced anxiety in learning	4.25	0.729	0.710	0.948
Less hesitation to participate	4.28	0.790	0.713	0.948
Encouraged to contribute and collaborate	4.21	0.751	0.797	0.947
Increased interest in learning	4.23	0.762	0.750	0.948

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

```

jmv::cfa(
  data = data,
  factors = list(
    list(
      label="Comprehension Dimensions",
      vars=c(
        "Understand teacher clearly",
        "Follow along the lecture",
        "Comprehend sentences and expression",
        "Understand unfamiliar vocabulary",
        "Save time understanding the lesson",
        "Identify grammar patterns",
        "Feeling less lost in the discussion",
        "Focus better in the lesson",
        "Easy to recall lesson content",
        "Complete assigned task accurately")),
    list(
      label="Engagement and Participation",
      vars=c(
        "Engaged in class",
        "Confident to participate",
        "Encouraged to ask question",
        "Focused on class discussion",
        "Reduced anxiety in learning",
        "Less hesitation to participate",
        "Encouraged to contribute and collaborate",
        "Increased interest in learning"))),
  resCov = NULL,
  fitMeasures = c(

```

"cfi",
 "tli",
 "rmsea",
 "srmr",
 "aic",
 "bic"))

Factor Loadings

Factor	Indicator	Estimate	SE	Z	p
Comprehension Dimensions	Understand teacher clearly	0.520	0.0435	12.0	<.001
	Follow along the lecture	0.566	0.0429	13.2	<.001
	Comprehend sentences and expression	0.589	0.0456	12.9	<.001
	Understand unfamiliar vocabulary	0.495	0.0452	10.9	<.001
	Save time understanding the lesson	0.623	0.0450	13.9	<.001
	Identify grammar patterns	0.592	0.0506	11.7	<.001
	Feeling less lost in the discussion	0.561	0.0430	13.1	<.001
	Focus better in the lesson	0.543	0.0471	11.5	<.001
	Easy to recall lesson content	0.592	0.0428	13.8	<.001
Engagement and Participation	Complete assigned task accurately	0.578	0.0444	13.0	<.001
	Engaged in class	0.593	0.0466	12.7	<.001
	Confident to participate	0.650	0.0453	14.4	<.001
	Encouraged to ask question	0.590	0.0456	13.0	<.001
	Focused on class discussion	0.650	0.0427	15.2	<.001
	Reduced anxiety in learning	0.598	0.0403	14.8	<.001
	Less hesitation to participate	0.602	0.0453	13.3	<.001
	Encouraged to contribute and collaborate	0.638	0.0407	15.7	<.001
	Increased interest in learning	0.637	0.0417	15.3	<.001

Factor Estimates

Factor Covariances

		Estimate	SE	Z	p
Comprehension Dimensions	Comprehension Dimensions	1.000 ^a			
	Engagement and Participation	0.788	0.0308	25.6	<.001
Engagement and Participation	Engagement and Participation	1.000 ^a			

^a fixed parameter

Model Fit

Test for Exact Fit

χ^2	df	p
273	134	<.001

Fit Measures

CFI	TLI	SRMR	RMSEA	RMSEA 90% CI		AIC	BIC
				Lower	Upper		
0.949	0.942	0.0410	0.0680	0.0563	0.0795	6833	7020